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Oncogenic chromosomal fusions are sufficient to activate ECT2.

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We demonstrate here that the SSX-SS18 fusion found in synovial sarcoma is sufficient to activate ECT2 *in vitro*. Together, we have demonstrated sufficiency of tumor suppressor loss, oncogene activation, and oncogenic chromosomal fusion expression as common denominators in induction of transformation in solid tissues.